

ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF TECHNOLOGY IN PREPARING PUPILS FOR EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF FOLK CRAFTS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the characteristics of educating pupils with an active moral attitude towards technology, as a means of forming artistic abilities in creative activity, and organizing pupils' independent work on folk crafts.*

Keywords: *folk crafts, independent education, practical skills, artistic and practical activities, national perception, educational process.*

Modern society needs qualified, enthusiastic, active specialists with rich creative and professional capabilities. The increase in the level of professional training among pupils in painting, composition, applied arts and crafts, folk crafts depends very much on the knowledge they receive in these fields in general education schools and, of course, on the development of their abilities on the basis of independent work.

It is known that crafts and folk crafts have become one of the central directions of folk art that was created in ancient times. Taking this into account, in today's modern general education schools, it is appropriate to arouse great interest in this matter among pupils, to use various methods and advanced ideas to improve their creative competence. In this case, effective and appropriate use of independent education also serves to achieve high results.

Independent education is very useful for pupils' complete freedom for creative activity, in-depth knowledge of technology and folk crafts, in understanding of the surrounding reality, formation of practical skills and competencies, development of artistic and practical skills, in systematic and purposeful development of national perception, as well as in the development of spatial thinking, compositional structure, fantasy and combinatory image. It is only necessary to know where to use independent education when organizing practical lessons.

In order to organize the pedagogical-experimental work of the master's thesis under the theme "Methodology of developing pupils' interest in national handicrafts based on the cluster approach", it was considered necessary to apply various methods. And while not departing from this basis, the goal of the experimental work is to organize independent education in the preparation of general secondary school pupils in the direction of technology to educating them in technology classes on the basis of folk crafts, to determine the level of effective use of pedagogic conditions that allow them to develop factors that encourage independent education.

The following tasks have been solved in accordance with the set goal:

- study and generalization of theoretical information on the organization of independent education of pupils in the educational process based on the study educational normative documents (State educational standard, curriculum, subject programs, etc.) that illuminate the process of formation of knowledge and skills related to folk crafts in pupils in the direction of technology in general secondary educational institutions;

- determination of the information about the mastery of the basic concepts of the essence of the process of organizing the education of pupils based on folk crafts in technology classes using questionnaires;
- study of the level of knowledge and skills formation in educating pupils on the basis of folk crafts in labor education classes directly on the example of the topics of the subject of "technology" and with the help of tasks given for independent completion;
- achieving the formation of educational characteristics in the educating pupils based on folk crafts in the technology classes of general secondary school pupils.

Experimental works based on the recommendations and instructions given in the scientific works of K.M.Abdullayeva, V.P.Bespalko, N.A.Muslimov, U.N.Nishonaliyev, SH.S.Sharipov, O.A.Koysynov and other pedagogues-scientists have been carried out according to the state educational standards and educational goals. At the same time, the types of independent education suitable for scientific research have been addressed.

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